

Low-Cost Communication Solution with Voice over Internet Protocol

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Abstract—VoIP University is a communication solution based on the IP protocol. This solution was proposed to modernize and save on communication, which required the development of Android, iOS, and Windows applications and a web service server. This solution allows integration with management system databases to create and manage a list of user extensions. VoIP UEMA was the first deployed project of VoIP University. A mean opinion score test was done, and the results indicated good quality. A financial analysis revealed that annual spending on telephone bills decreased by more than 97%.

Keywords—VoIP eTec, VoIP UEMA, VoIP University, VoIP Valen.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS paper presents the first five projects of the VoIP university solution. This work was supported by FAPEMA (Foundation to Support Scientific Research and Development of Maranhão - Brazil).

VoIP university is an IP communication solution that utilizes VoIP [1]-[4] and IP (Internet Protocol) connections to accomplish quadruple-play communication to voice, data, and video with mobility based on a client-server model with two servers, one for authentication and the other for user registration.

The first project of the VoIP university solution was called VoIP UEMA and consists of the VoIP UEMA web service server, the VoIP UEMA SIP server for signaling, the SIGUEMA academic and administration system server, the VoIP UEMA Application (App), the VoIP UEMA webphone, and the VoIP UEMA web page [5].

The next sections are organized as follows. Related works are presented in Section II. Section III presents VoIP university technical aspects. Section IV presents the VoIP UEMA project. Section V presents VoIP UEMA technical aspects. Section VI presents the VoIP Pitágoras project. In Section VII, the VoIP Gov MA project is presented. Section VIII presents the VoIP eTec project. Section IX presents the VoIP Valen project. Section X presents the Mean Opinion Score (MOS). Section XI presents a financial analysis. Section XII presents considerations about innovation. Finally, in Section XIII, the conclusion is presented.

II. RELATED WORKS

VoIP university starts with the low-cost solution concept

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based on freeware infrastructure, which includes some softphones (CounterPath X-Lite, Mizudroid, Zoiper, and SessionTalk SIP) as well as enterprise and carrier equipment based on the Asterisk on the Linux operating system (FreePBX).

Communication among clients (softphones, IP telephones, and legacy fixed/conventional telephones) has become possible. To our knowledge, the VoIP UEMA project developed its softphones and automated the entire control procedure via the VoIP UEMA web service, which plays the VoIP UEMA user administrator role.

III. VOIP UNIVERSITY TECHNICAL ASPECTS

The technical aspects of the VoIP university solution are as follows.

A. Web Service

A web service is a software system used for system integration based on some communication languages such as Extensible Markup Language (XML), JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), and Concurrent Versions System (CVS) capable of maintaining machine-to-machine communication over a network.

It can present an interface that describes it as Web Services Description Language (WSDL), and Web Application Description Language (WADL), and communicate through protocols such as Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP), usually using Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) with XML serialization. There are two types of web services, the WS-* family web services, and the Representational State Transfer (REST) architecture-based web services.

The WS-* architecture consists of more than 20 specifications as SOAP, WSDL, and Universal Description, Discovery, and Integration (UDDI). In addition to these, there are WS-Notification, WS-Addressing, WS-Transfer, WS-Policy, WS-Security, WS-Trust, WS-Reliable Messaging, WS Transfer, WS-I Basic Profile, WS-Transaction, and others. One of the main complaints about this format concerns the large number of specifications making learning complex and bureaucratic [6].

REST-based web services use the HTTP protocol because it has all the semantics needed to handle operations. The only disadvantage of this type of web service is that by keeping the interface uniform, the request cannot be changed and suited for each type of request.

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The JSON language was adopted to the web service VoIP UEMA because it is the lightest and most widely used language worldwide.

B. HTTP

HTTP is a stateless application-level request/response protocol that uses extensive semantics and self-describing messages for flexible interaction with network-based information systems.

A client is a program that establishes a connection to a server by sending one or more requests. Chrome, Firefox, and Internet

Explorer browsers [7] are popular clients.

A server is a program that accepts connections to service requests by sending responses.

Fig. 1 shows an example of a simple HTTP transaction. Using the Google Chrome browser, it is possible to make a transaction with the server that hosts the academic management system of the State University of Maranhão. In the first line, the browser states that it wants the GET method to be executed. The server responds to status 200 with a callout “OK”, informing the data and how to interpret it.

Request Header

```
GET /sigaa/verTelaLogin.do;jsessionid=CEE2D72D84CE1BFAFEA696E86C17182E.s211 HTTP/1.1
Host: sis.sig.uema.br
User-Agent: Mozilla/5.0 (Macintosh; U; Intel Mac OS X; de-de) AppleWebKit/523.10.3 (KHTML, like Gecko) Version/3.0.4 Safari/523.10
Connection: close
```

Response Header

```
HTTP/1.1 200 OK
Date: Sat, 20 May 2017 16:43:53 GMT
Server: Apache
Vary: Accept-Encoding
Connection: close
Transfer-Encoding: chunked
Content-Type: text/html; charset=ISO-8859-1
```

Fig. 1 HTTP transaction

Fig. 2 Traditional VoIP Structure

C. VoIP

VoIP is a method to deliver multimedia sessions as packets over IP networks, such as the Internet [1].

Signaling is based on protocols such as SIP, H.323, and Media Gateway Control Protocol (MGCP), and multimedia communication is based on protocols such as Real-time Transport Protocol (RTP), Real-time Control Protocol (RTCP), and Real-Time Streaming Protocol (RTSP), all of them performed by a VoIP server.

The VoIP traffic can occur securely by encrypting the data with protocols such as SRTP and ZRTP [4]. Fig. 2 shows an example of a simple VoIP network. IP telephone and softphones, present in the notebook and desktop, are addressed on the network and authenticated on the server. The server plays the

role of media and signaling communication.

The VoIP server adopted in the VoIP UEMA project is Asterisk, a freeware server based on SIP protocol that has several built-in servers (email, firewall, VoIP, etc.) and provides media and signaling communications and Call Detail Records (CDR).

D. Database

A Database Management System (DBMS) is software that incorporates data definition, retrieval, and alteration functions into a database [8]. A relational DBMS organizes all data into tables. One of the most complete free distribution DBMSs on the market is MySQL which was adopted as the VoIP UEMA web service DBMS.

A database project takes place in two phases:

- Conceptual modeling: In this first phase, a conceptual model is constructed as an entity-relationship diagram. This model captures the stored university data regardless of implementation.
- Logical design: The logical design stage aims to transform the conceptual model obtained in the first phase into a logical model. The logical model defines how the database is implemented in a specific DBMS.

The most widespread and widely used data modeling technique is the Entity-Relationship (ER) approach. In this technique, the data model is represented by an ER model. Usually, an ER model is graphically represented by an Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD). The ER approach was created in 1976 [9].

An entity is a set of modeled objects to be kept in the database. A relationship is a set of associations between entities.

Cardinality is the number (minimum and maximum) of entity occurrences associated with an occurrence of the entity in question through the relationship. Attribute is the data that are associated with each occurrence of an entity or relationship. Entity identifier or primary key is a set of attributes and relationships whose values distinguish one entity instance from the others. A foreign key is the field that establishes the relationship between entities.

IV. VoIP UEMA PROJECT

VoIP UEMA project [5] was deployed in the State University of Maranhão (UEMA) to all students, professors, and administrative technicians in all 20 campuses and 22 centers connected through the same data center, without requiring SIP call routing.

VoIP UEMA Applications were developed for smartphones with Android [10], iPhone OS (iOS) [11], and Windows [12] operating systems and allow users of the UEMA community to make voice and video calls among them and to wireless, fixed, and IP telephones.

VoIP Uema is innovative because its web service server is integrated with the SIGUEMA system. All the extensions are found in a list to facilitate user searches by name, identification number (ID), job role, course, center, and campus. This integration allows a VoIP UEMA user to log in with the same system credentials (login and password) and make voice or video calls with a simple tap after an extension search. The user

database is automatically updated, and the extensions list is maintained up to date considering the entrance and exit of students, professors, and administrative staff at the university.

The VoIP UEMA webphone is hosted on the VoIP UEMA web page [13], which is hosted on the UEMA official website [14].

The VoIP UEMA project has user and service extensions for voice and video communications with people, departments, laboratories, and course secretaries. Furthermore, unlike WhatsApp, which generates costs with WhatsApp Business, there is no cost for the university to call service extensions.

All four other VoIP university projects (Pitágoras, Gov MA, eTec, and Valen) shown in the next items are derived from the VoIP UEMA project. A customization was made in the VoIP UEMA project to obtain the other ones.

V. VoIP UEMA TECHNICAL ASPECTS

The VoIP UEMA project goal is to allow the use of the same SIGUEMA credentials (login and password) for user authentication in the VoIP UEMA network and keep the extensions list up to date considering the entrance and exit of students, professors, and administrative staff at the university.

An adaptation of the traditional VoIP telephony was a strong requirement, where authentication will first pass through an intermediary web service and after this the necessary steps to create a user extension list, as detailed in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 VoIP UEMA Architecture

A. SIGUEMA Web Service

After all the authentications are obtained, the VoIP UEMA web service can query the remaining data from the SIGUEMA

web service which provides an API at the URL for querying user data. It is possible to send an HTTP request with the GET method containing the ID and hash of the user password

VoIP service operation with all extensions.

C. Authentication API for VoIP UEMA Users

Considering the VoIP UEMA database and all extensions on the Asterisk server already created (phases 1 to 4 shown in Fig. 3), it is necessary to build an API so that VoIP UEMA users can authenticate using SIGUEMA credentials (phases 5 and 6 shown in Fig. 3).

For security reasons, user passwords are not stored, so after receiving user credentials, they are passed to the SIGUEMA web service for authentication.

The HTTP request used for authentication is the same one used for collecting extra information reported in Subsection 4.1. If the credentials are invalid, the return from the SIGUEMA web service will be the same as shown in Fig. 7.

The API will implement the REST architecture with return in JSON and will be available at the URI and the user must send a request with the POST method, followed by the user ID and their

```
{
  "nome": "LUIZ RICARDO SOUZA RIPARDO",
  "ramais": {
    "aluno": {
      "curso": "ENGENHARIA DA COMPUTAÇÃO",
      "centro": "CENTRO DE CIÊNCIAS TECNOLÓGICAS",
      "unidade": "CENTRO DE CIÊNCIAS TECNOLÓGICAS",
      "ramal": "00000000",
      "modalidade": "Presencial"
    },
    "servidor_admin": {
    },
    "servidor_academico": {
    }
  }
}
```

password registered in SIGUEMA.

```
{
  "meta": {
    "code": 204,
    "warning_message": "Login and/or password are not valid system user"
  }
}
```

Fig. 7 Return from SIGUEMA web service to report failed login

Upon confirmation of valid credentials by the SIGUEMA web service, the VoIP UEMA web service will return to the client the login information (extensions, passwords, VoIP server address, etc.) for the VoIP service as shown in Fig. 8. Thus, the client will follow the direct flow with the Asterisk VoIP server and the VoIP service will be released.

```
{
  "nome": "CARLOS HENRIQUE RODRIGUES DE OLIVEIRA",
  "ramais": {
    "aluno": {
    },
    "servidor_academico": {
      "categoria": "Docente",
      "centro": "CENTRO DE CIÊNCIAS TECNOLÓGICAS",
      "unidade": "ENGENHARIA DE COMPUTACAO-BACHARELADO",
      "cargo": "ASSISTENTE I",
      "ramal": "0000000"
    }
  }
}
```

Fig. 8 Example of extensions return

D. Visibility of Extensions

VoIP UEMA users will have the option to remove their extension from the list if they wish. This change can be dynamic meaning that at any time the user can re-enter their extension in the list.

The VoIP UEMA web service has an API available at the URI, to receive client requests with visibility information in the extension list.

A PUT method must be performed, with a JSON attached in the body, informing the extension and a Boolean value, true or false, to be visible or not, as shown in Fig. 9.

```
{
  "extension": "0000000",
  "visible": "false"
}
```

Fig. 9 Example of the body for extension removal request

E. Request Security

It is important to emphasize that all requests shown so far are performed through application-only knowledge authentication headers, thus ensuring that the web service accepts and executes

only requests from clients in possession of these headers.

F. Database Modeling

For extension list storage, modeling must be performed considering the information necessary for VoIP operation. The modeling is shown in Fig. 10 where id: the primary key to identify each record; cpf: user identification in SIGUEMA; name: full username provided by SIGUEMA.

Fig. 10 Database modeling using MySQL Workbench software

G. VoIP UEMA Web Service

According to Fig. 3, the first step in creating the VoIP UEMA user database is to get all users registered in SIGUEMA. The initial idea is to create a database with all users and their extension information such as name, identification number (ID), job role, course, center, and campus. To get this information, the

web service must perform a query on the SIGUEMA server.

The VoIP UEMA web service was developed in Java language. It uses an Apache Tomcat web server for hosting and an Apache web server as a proxy. The web resources are available in [15].

VoIP UEMA is a trademark in the National Institute of Industrial Property (INPI) [16].

H. VoIP UEMA Application

A freeware softphone for the Google Android operating system called VoIP UEMA App, available on the Play Store, has been developed to make VoIP and video calls based on the PJSIP library.

The App allows authentication with SIGUEMA credentials, through the VoIP UEMA web service, and the connection to the VoIP UEMA SIP server, allowing SIP calls with good quality.

The key features of this software are:

- A plug-in adds support for voice calling with Opus codec.
- A plug-in adds support for video calling with H.264 codec.
- Good loss robustness and packet loss concealment (PLC).
- Security and encryption with SRTP based on the OpenSSH Library.

It used Android Studio IDE (Integrated Development Environment) and Java programming language for the softphone development.

The application achieved the objectives of successfully authenticating the users in VoIP UEMA web service and Asterisk servers using their SIGUEMA credentials and establishing optimal audio and video streaming.

The App presentation screen is shown in Fig. 11. The direct call button allows anyone outside of the academic community to call some sectors of the university with no login, bringing social benefits.

Fig. 11 App presentation screen

I. VoIP UEMA Webphone

The VoIP UEMA webphone presentation screen is shown in Fig. 12. It was developed based on Web Real-Time Communication (Web RTC), a free and open project that provides browsers and mobile applications with real-time communication capabilities via APIs. The voice codec used is Opus.

VoIP UEMA App and the webphone allow the users to disable their visibility in the extension lists. In addition, the App allows blocking any user of the extension list.

VoIP
UEMA

webphone

SIGUEMA Users: _____

Password: _____

enter

Fig. 12 VoIP UEMA webphone presentation screen

J. VoIP UEMA Web Page

Fig. 13 VoIP UEMA web page presentation screen

The VoIP UEMA web page presentation screen is shown in Fig. 13. The page contains a presentation of VoIP UEMA, the

project team, a link to the webphone, some contacts, UEMA news, and a FAQ.

VI. VOIP PITÁGORAS PROJECT

Pitágoras is a college present in several states in Brazil. The VoIP Pitágoras project is also a cloud service, as shown in Fig. 14 topology [17], and is based on the VoIP UEMA project. The VoIP Pitágoras web service and SIP servers can be physically hosted on a server either in the cloud or locally close to the router and are used for user authentication and registration, respectively.

A. VoIP Pitágoras Application

The VoIP Pitágoras application is based on the VoIP UEMA application [5].

A freeware softphone for the Android operating system called the VoIP Pitágoras Application was developed to enable VoIP and video calls.

The app allows for authentication with the Pitágoras academic/administrative credentials through the VoIP Pitágoras web service and for registration with the VoIP Pitágoras SIP server, allowing for SIP calls with the MOS metric.

The key features of this software are as follows:

- A plug-in adds support for voice calling with the Opus codec.
- A plug-in adds support for video calling with the H.264 codec.
- Good loss robustness and packet loss concealment (PLC) were achieved.
- Security and encryption with Secure Real-time Transport Protocol based on the Open Secure Socket Shell Library are applied.

The Android Studio IDE (Integrated Development Environment) and Java programming languages were used for softphone development.

The application achieved the objectives of successfully authenticating the users on the VoIP Pitágoras web service server registering the users on the Asterisk server using their Pitágoras academic/administrative credentials and establishing audio and video streaming.

The VoIP Pitágoras project topology is shown in Fig. 14.

The VoIP Pitágoras App presentation screen is shown in Fig. 15.

There is an app privacy feature that allows users to disable their visibility in extension lists. In addition, the app allows blocking any user in the extension list.

VII. VOIP GOV MA PROJECT

This project aimed to modernize the communication network of the state of Maranhão departments and contribute to reducing expenses associated with communication services by at least 30% in each body or entity, provided for in State Decree nº 34,579 of November 23, 2018, to determine measures aimed at reducing funding expenses within the scope of direct and indirect public administration.

The VoIP Gov MA Project is also a cloud service based on the VoIP UEMA project. The VoIP Gov MA web service and

SIP servers can be physically hosted on a server either in the cloud or locally close to the router and are used for user authentication and registration, respectively.

Fig. 14 VoIP Pitágoras project topology

Fig. 15 App presentation screen

A. VoIP Gov MA Application

The VoIP Gov MA application is based on the VoIP UEMA application. Fig. 16 shows the window at which the VoIP Gov MA user extension list was downloaded.

Fig. 16 VoIP Gov MA App user extension list

Fig. 17 VoIP Gov MA App echo test

Fig. 17 shows the VoIP Gov MA App echo test window after

dialing *43. Fig. 18 shows the recent call list window of the VoIP Gov MA App. Fig. 19 shows the VoIP Gov MA App contact list window.

Fig. 18 Recent calls on the VoIP Gov MA App

Fig. 19 VoIP Gov MA App contact list

Fig. 20 shows the registered user window highlighted in green color. Fig. 21 shows the extension visibility window of the VoIP

Gov MA App.

Fig. 20 The VoIP Gov MA App registered user

Fig. 21 VoIP Gov MA App extension visibility

B. VoIP Gov MA Webphone

The VoIP Gov MA webphone is based on the VoIP UEMA webphone [5]. Fig. 22 shows the VoIP Gov MA webphone presentation window.

Fig. 22 The VoIP Gov MA webphone presentation window

Fig. 23 shows the recent calls list window of the VoIP Gov MA webphone. Fig. 24 shows the VoIP Gov MA webphone echo test window after dialing *43. Fig. 25 shows the call in the

progress window of the VoIP Gov MA webphone. Fig. 26 shows the incoming call window of the VoIP Gov MA webphone.

Extension	Number	Date/time	Description	Duration	Tags
9902	9902	13/10/2019 10:16:20	Vocal 190w	00:00:10	📞
*43	*43	13/10/2019 10:06:47	Vocal 190w	00:00:06	📞

Fig. 23 Recent calls on the VoIP Gov MA webphone

Fig. 24 VoIP Gov MA webphone echo test

Fig. 25 VoIP Gov MA webphone call in progress

Fig. 27 shows the registered user window highlighted in green color. Fig. 28 shows the VoIP Gov MA user extensions window.

VIII. VOIP ETEC PROJECT

eTec is the Federal Council of Industrial Technicians. More than four decades ago, a group of technicians began working to

regulate the professional category – Law n°. 5,524/1968 and Decree No. 90,922/1985 – to create its council. On March 26, 2018, the presidential sanction of Law n°. 13,639/2018 represented a historic achievement and the realization of the beginning of a new era, with greater security for society and professional development for millions of technicians, duly recognized as professionals.

Fig. 26 VoIP Gov MA webphone incoming call

Fig. 27 VoIP Gov MA webphone registered user

The initial objective of the VoIP eTEC project was to provide a modern communication system for 60 to 100 thousand users and to connect five offices, starting with the receptions and providing two to three extensions. In response to this demand, the VoIP eTec was proposed.

The VoIP eTec Project is also a cloud service based on the VoIP UEMA project. The VoIP eTec web service and SIP

servers can be physically hosted on a server either in the cloud or locally close to the router and are used for user authentication and registration, respectively.

One proof of concept of the VoIP eTec Project was proposed based on the network topology presented in Fig. 30 and a testbed presented in Fig. 31.

Name	Extension	State	Secretaries	Role
ABRAHAO	9917	State of Maranhão	SEATI	Assessor
ADILON	9900	State of Maranhão	SEGEF	Secretary
ALESSANDRO	9927	State of Maranhão	SEATI	Server
ANA CRISTINA	9901	State of Maranhão	SEPLAN	Server
ANA PAULA	9902	State of Maranhão	UEMA	Project manager
ANDERSON	9903	State of Maranhão	SEATI	Server
ANDRE	9930	State of Maranhão	SEATI	Server
ANDREA	9904	State of Maranhão	SEATI	Server
CARLOS HENRIQUE	9905	State of Maranhão	UEMA	Project manager

Fig. 28 VoIP Gov MA user extensions

Extension	Type	Visible in the extension list
9905	server	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Save

Fig. 29 The VoIP Gov MA webphone extension visibility

The concept was proven, and it was possible to make calls from/to analog/digital telephones, allowing legacy telephony integration.

According to Anatel, in 2020, the number of fixed lines in Brazil was 38.5 million. This represents an enormous opportunity for solutions to integrate with legacy conventional telephony devices before switching to IPs and mobile phones.

IX. VOIP VALEN PROJECT

The Valen Post is in the port of Itaqui in the state of Maranhão and is one of the most important ports in Brazil. There are 120 thousand square meters, 12 fuel pumps for light vehicles and 16 for large vehicles, convenience stores, warehouses, 26 commercial stores, pharmacies, hotels, 73 executive standard apartments, and parking with 600 spaces. It is open 24 hours a

day and offers the Estrada Club, an area with free access for truck drivers, internet, barber shops, infirmaries, games tables, and a cinema.

The VoIP Valen Project is also a cloud service based on the VoIP UEMA project. The VoIP Valen web service and SIP servers can be physically hosted on a server either in the cloud or locally close to the router and are used for user authentication and registration, respectively. This was the second project of VoIP university that was deployed.

A fixed-line PABX was being used and for this reason, it was necessary to install a VoIP gateway to allow the integration of the legacy telephony with the VoIP Valen App. It was necessary to customize the VoIP Valen web service for some test extensions, as shown in Fig. 32.

Fig. 30 VoIP eTec project topology

Fig. 31 Testbed to the VoIP eTec Project

Fig. 32 VoIP Valen web service for test extensions

n	MOS
4	1
0	1.5
1	2
0	2.5
8	3
3	3.5
20	4
2	4.5
1	5

Fig. 33 MOS test results

X. MEAN OPINION SCORE [18]

MOS measures subjective voice quality for a call. MOS scores range from 1 for unacceptable to 5 for excellent. VOIP calls often are in the 3.5 to 4.2 range.

35 people were invited to participate in a MOS test by calling each other using VoIP UEMA App and VoIP UEMA web phone (both with Opus voice codec) over Wi-Fi and wired networks (both with average data rates above 10 Mbit/s) as well as 4G (average data rates of 15 Mbit/s).

Fig. 33 shows the MOS test results with a weighted average around 3.5.

The attendees' comments to MOS 3 to 5 range were: clean and uncut-out voice calls like Skype and WhatsApp because the used codec is the same (Opus). However, the three applications depend on the network quality.

The comments to MOS 1 to 2.5 range were: cut-out voice calls. These results are related to the network quality of service.

XI. FINANCIAL ANALYSIS

It is worth noting that the financial analysis presented in [5] has the potential to be achieved in other projects of VoIP university.

Considering 2013, 2014, and 2015, UEMA had an average annual phone bill expense of R\$ 1.256.624,30 (US\$ 312,500.00), as shown in Fig. 34.

Fig. 34 The average annual phone bill expenses of UEMA over 3 years

Two years after the deployment of the VoIP UEMA project, the annual phone bill expense dropped to US\$ 9,000, representing savings of over 97 %.

The low-cost solution is justified because there was no expense associated with the materials or equipment, and only professors and students were paid with scholarships.

XII. INNOVATION

The VoIP university projects innovate because, in a bibliographical search, it did not find a voice and video communication system over the IP protocol using the SIP protocol for signaling that allows the integration of the web service module with the academic and corporate management system and user authentication with the same credentials on both systems. This makes using the solution easier. With a simple touch, it is possible to make a call after searching the extension list, and it relieves the burden of updating users entering and leaving the institution because the update is done by the web service (WS) via SIGUEMA automatically and more practical than Fone RNP [19], a VoIP communication system, which depends on an extension plan and manual effort to update user extensions due to the users entering and leaving the system.

There are four Computer Program Registration (RPC) applications in the INPI with the following registrations: a) the VoIP UEMA web service with process number BR 51 2017 001608-9; b) the VoIP UEMA App with process number BR 51 2017 001614-3; c) the VoIP UEMA webphone with process number BR 51 2018 000820-8; and d) the VoIP UEMA web page with process number BR 51 2017 001606-2.

XIII. CONCLUSION

VoIP university is a project that has been producing meaningful results. It started in 2015 and currently has two college degree monographs, three professional Master of Science dissertations, six scholarships for students, one university extension project with scholarships for one student, and five IP communication projects, two of which have already been deployed (VoIP UEMA and VoIP Valen).

VoIP university is a solution with maturity and extensive operational experience, providing confidence and financial security to the other projects presented in this work and possibly others in the future.

VoIP UEMA is the first project available to more than 20,000 students, 1,400 teachers, and administrative technicians. Nowadays, communication occurs more via the VoIP UEMA network than via public fixed and mobile telephone networks. The VoIP UEMA App has over 1,000 downloads and more than 300 registered service extensions in laboratories, libraries, and departments. Two years after the deployment of the VoIP UEMA project, the average annual phone bill expense dropped from US\$ 312,500.00 to US\$ 9,000.00, which means more than 97 % savings.

It is worth mentioning that this solution is open to other institutions.

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